

RESEARCH OF INTELLIGENT SYSTEMS FOR PROTECTION AGAINST NETWORK ATTACKS

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Abstract. Today, computer networks, including local ones, continue to develop rapidly. However, security in these networks often does not meet the required level, since computer infrastructure objects have vulnerabilities and are susceptible to various network attacks. One of the most relevant means of protection against computer attacks is attack detection systems. At the same time, thanks to the wide capabilities of data mining methods, the task of analyzing network traffic parameters for signs of an attack can be solved using these methods. The article provides an overview of attacks that are relevant for local computer networks, proposes an architecture for an attack detection system based on data mining methods, and also compares these methods for detecting the types of attacks under consideration. The experimental results allow us to draw a conclusion about the practical significance of the proposed approach to detecting attacks in local computer networks.

Keywords: local network, network attack, detection module, intelligent data analysis, signature, computer technology

Introduction

Computer networks[24-33] were first created in the late 1950s for use in the military and defense. They were originally used to transmit data over telephone lines and had limited commercial and scientific applications. With the advent of Internet technologies, a computer network has become indispensable for enterprises.

Today's network solutions provide more than connectivity. Today they are critical to digital transformation and business success. Core networking capabilities have become more programmable, automated, and secure.

See below for the capabilities of modern computer networks.

Virtual Operations. The underlying physical network infrastructure can be logically separated to create multiple overlay networks. In an overlay computer network, nodes are virtually connected and data can be transferred between them over multiple physical paths. For example, many corporate networks overlap the Internet.

Large scale integration. Modern network services connect physically distributed computer networks. These services can optimize network functions through automation and monitoring to create one large-scale, high-performance network. Network services can be increased or decreased depending on demand.

Quick response to changing conditions. Many computer networks are software-defined. Traffic can be directed and controlled centrally using a digital interface. These computer networks support virtual traffic control.

Data security protection. All network solutions come with built-in security features such as encryption and access control. Third-party solutions such as antivirus software, firewalls and anti-malware can be integrated to make the network more secure.

Some interesting facts about computer networking are:

- Internet was invented by ARPANET in 1983.
- Internet is controlled by 75 million servers.
- The backbone of the internet is made by 550, 000 miles of underwater cable.
- About one billion computer systems are connected to the internet.
- About 3.2 billion people use the internet from which 1.7 billion internet users are Asians.
- The Internet consists of five billion computing devices such as computers, phones, modems, switches, routers, etc.
- According to Google, the Internet consists of 5 million Terabytes of data.
- If the internet goes down for a day, approximately 200 billion emails and 3 billion Google searches would have to wait.
- Approximately 204 million emails per minute are sent over the Internet. 70% of them are spam.
- 269 billion emails are sent per day.
- 30, 000 websites are hacked every day.
- 50 million horsepower is required by the internet to keep running in the current state.
- Approximately 9 million adults in Britain and 1/3rd of Italians have never used the internet while China has treatment camps for internet addicts.
- Microsoft has more servers than Google. Microsoft owns over one million servers while Google has 900, 000.

- Internet bots and malware generate 61.5% or nearly two-thirds of all the website traffic.
- Approximately 1.7 trillion euro dollars worth of funds is spent online.
- Tim Berners-Lee was knighted by Queen Elizabeth.
- An email takes around 2 billion electrons to produce.
- Online dating generates approximately \$1 billion dollars every year.
- Qwerty was designed to slow you down so that the keys would not jam while using a TypeWriter, for which the layout was originally made.
- The first ever message sent over the Internet was sent by computer scientist, Vint Cerf in 1969. The message read, "Lo".
- The first website, info.cern.ch, was created in 1991 by Tim Berners-Lee, the inventor of the World Wide Web.
- The first online sale was made by Stan O'Neal in 1994, when he sold a CD of Sting's album "Ten Summoner's Tales" over the Internet.
- The first social media site, Six Degrees, was launched in 1997.
- The number of Internet users worldwide surpassed 4 billion in 2021.
- The Internet of Things (IoT) refers to the connection of everyday devices to the Internet, allowing for the exchange of data between them. It is estimated that there will be 75 billion IoT devices by 2025.
- The fastest Internet speeds are found in South Korea, with an average connection speed of 28.6 Mbps.
- The Internet carries an estimated 100 petabytes of data per day, equivalent to around 100 million gigabytes.
- The most popular website in the world is Google, with over 92% of the global search engine market share.
- The most popular social media site is Facebook, with over 2.8 billion monthly active users as of 2021.
- The world's first webcam was invented in 1991 by a team at Cambridge University. It was used to monitor a coffee pot so that people could see if there was any coffee left before making the trip to the break room.
- The first emoticon was invented in 1982 by computer scientist Scott Fahlman. He suggested using ☺ to indicate a joke in online communication.

- The concept of a “virus” in computing was first introduced by Fred Cohen in 1983. He created a self-replicating program that could infect other computers.
- The first Wi-Fi network was created in 1991 by a team at NCR Corporation. It was called WaveLAN and used radio waves to transmit data.
- The first mobile phone with internet access was the Nokia 9000 Communicator, released in 1996. It had a built-in web browser and email client.
- The first commercial text message was sent in 1992 by Neil Papworth, who was working for Vodafone at the time. The message simply said “Merry Christmas.”
- The domain name “Google” was actually a mistake. The founders of the company originally intended to call it “Googol,” which is a mathematical term for the number 1 followed by 100 zeroes. However, they misspelled it when registering the domain name and decided to stick with the new version.
- The term “spam” for unwanted email originated from a Monty Python sketch in which a group of Vikings sing a song about spam.
- The world’s first banner ad was placed on the HotWired website in 1994. It was a simple message that read “Have you ever clicked your mouse right here? You will.”
- The first YouTube video was uploaded in 2005 by co-founder Jawed Karim. It was called “Me at the zoo” and showed him standing in front of some elephants.

Main part.

IDS[1,2] provide one-by-one scanning of channels for active attacks. Decision-making about the security of any network[3-14] activity in commercial products is implemented using closed algorithms, the operating principle[15-23] of which is a commercial secret. At the same time, the stated number and types of detected attacks differ among different products, although in reality they belong to the same type of attacks, which is explained by the lack of standards in the field of computer attacks.

As was shown in the works mentioned above, the problems of detecting and classifying attacks can be solved using IDA methods, which allow identifying significant correlations, patterns and trends in large volumes of data. The proposed system uses algorithms for constructing a classification model based

on support vector machines, k-nearest neighbors, neural networks and decision trees.

Fig 1. Architecture of the attack detection system

The proposed architecture of an intelligent attack detection system has a modular scheme for organizing interaction between components with a dedicated sensor subsystem and centralized control through the administrator console. The system architecture is shown in Fig. 1.

The basis for identifying attacks is a knowledge base, the construction of which at the stage of initial system configuration is provided by the block for constructing a classifying model. The classification model is built based on the signatures of the training set and is then used to classify real network activity.

Conclusion

This research provides an overview of network attacks relevant to local networks, presents the architecture of a proposed attack detection system to recognize these attacks and the architecture developed to detect the types of attacks considered can be useful in such scientific research.

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